

Influence of Digital Skills on the Job Performance of Business Education Graduates in Bayelsa State.

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of digital skills on the job performance of business education graduates in Bayelsa State. Two research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey research was adopted for the study. The study involved a total of 158 respondents, consisting of 52 males and 106 females, all of whom were business education graduates. Given the relatively small size of the population, no sampling was necessary, allowing for the inclusion of every member of the population in the study. Data collection was facilitated using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher, titled “Influence of Digital Skills on the Job Performance of Business Education Graduates Questionnaire (IDSJPBEGQ).” To ensure the validity of the instrument, it was validated by three research specialists. Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded 0.80 and 0.82 for clusters 1 and 2 with an overall reliability index of 0.81 which showed that the instrument was reliable. The researcher used mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of study showed that digital marketing skills and social media digital skills significantly influence job performance of Business Education Graduates in Bayelsa State to a high extent. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended that educational institutions should integrate comprehensive digital marketing and social media skills training into the business education curriculum.

Keywords: Digital Skills, Job Performance, Business Education, Graduates, Bayelsa State

Introduction

Business education is a significant academic discipline that starts in junior secondary schools and continues through tertiary institutions in Nigeria and beyond. Its main objective is to equip students with essential business skills and learning capabilities to tackle emerging workplace challenges. According to Ordu and Abulkarim (2020), the aim of business education is to provide students with opportunities to develop relevant business skills, such as office technology and management, marketing, accounting, and entrepreneurship, if implemented effectively. Essentially, business education focuses on mastering various competencies, including office technology, management information systems, marketing, digital marketing, entrepreneurship,

cooperative studies, insurance, and accounting. Business education is vital in vocational and technical training, emphasizing the development of both soft and hard skills in graduates. Val-Ossai and Akpomi (2017) noted that business education is structured to prepare students for career entry and advancement, highlighting its focus on acquiring the necessary skills, knowledge, and competencies for professional success. Educational institutions offer a broad spectrum of skills, including business acumen, entrepreneurial abilities, online skills, teaching competencies, and digital proficiency, equipping learners with the tools necessary for success in the modern workforce and academic environments.

Institutions like colleges of education, polytechnics, and universities provide business education that equips students with essential skills for various business careers (Umoro, 2020). The rapid shift to digital technologies and knowledge-based skills, accelerated by the COVID-19 lockdown, has further emphasized the need for a solid educational foundation in adapting to modern business environments. This transition has accelerated due to the increased reliance on remote work, online education, and managing various life aspects, such as health, social interactions, and household tasks, through digital means. The pandemic has underscored the deficiencies in digital skills and highlighted the risks and lack of familiarity with various digital technologies for different uses. Businesses that could not adapt to these technologies faced significant challenges during the lockdown of 2020 (Umoro, 2020). Digital technologies and skills offer unprecedented opportunities to create new jobs, enhance productivity, increase incomes, and reduce poverty. As the demand for digital skills rises, existing and new job roles increasingly require these competencies. In countries like Nigeria, where unemployment and poverty are severe, digital skills are crucial.

Digital skills refer to a range of abilities that include not just isolated skills but a combination of behaviours, knowledge, work habits, personal traits, and critical understanding. According to Akpotohwo, Watchman, and Ogeibiri (2016), digital and entrepreneurial skills involve combining creative and innovative ideas with managerial and organizational competencies to address needs and generate wealth through meaningful employment. UNESCO (2023) defined digital skills as the ability to effectively and meaningfully handle digital technologies to access, organize, understand, integrate, communicate, evaluate, and generate information. These skills cover computer, ICT, and media competencies aimed at enhancing young people's critical perspectives and acquiring specific skills. Berger and Frey (2016) suggested that as technology evolves, the digital skills expected of graduates are also changing, with a growing emphasis on higher-level digital competencies rather than just technical abilities. Today's job market demands tertiary graduates to possess skills such as information and data management, digital security, cloud computing, word processing, spreadsheet proficiency, and internet usage. Digital skills are categorized into foundational skills, communication skills, information and content manipulation skills, and problem-solving skills, with additional essential skills including digital marketing, social media, computer evaluation, and word processing (Ezoem et al., 2024). These digital skills can be broadly divided into basic, intermediate, and advanced levels. However, the present study focused on digital marketing skills and social media digital skills.

Digital marketing involves promoting products or services through digital technologies, particularly on the Internet, via websites, apps, social media, search engines, and other digital channels. This practice gained prominence with the Internet's growth in the 1990s and offers an additional method for companies to engage with consumers and understand their behaviour. Digital marketing, which includes display advertising and mobile usage, allows businesses to

analyze marketing campaigns more effectively compared to traditional marketing (Yamin, 2017). Despite its benefits, digital marketing presents challenges (Barone, 2023). Scharl et al. (2015), Ryan and Jones (2018), and Pulizzi (2016) highlighted various digital marketing tools such as email marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), online advertising, affiliate marketing, mobile marketing, and content marketing. Possessing digital marketing skills allows business education graduates to leverage social media platforms through internet-connected devices to market products from home, creating opportunities for employment or self-employment.

Social media, while widely used, lacks a clear, singular definition. It involves sharing content through interactions on various platforms. Companies use social media to provide tools and services that connect customers and businesses (Grewal & Levy, 2013). Zeeshain and Hussain (2017) described social media as the use of web and mobile technologies to create, share, and consume information without geographical, social, political, or demographic restrictions, in a participatory and collaborative manner. Digital skills in the areas of marketing and social media skills play a crucial role in enhancing business education graduates' job performance by enabling them to effectively navigate and leverage technology in today's digitally-driven business environments.

Job performance refers to the effectiveness with which an individual fulfills the duties and responsibilities of their role, contributing to the overall goals and success of an organization. Campbell and Wiernik (2015) defined job performance as encompassing behaviors within employees' control that aid in achieving organizational objectives. Job performance is the degree to which an employee successfully accomplishes the tasks and responsibilities outlined in their job description, reflecting their efficiency, output quality, and alignment with organizational goals (Sonnetag & Frese, 2012). It encompasses both task performance, which refers to the technical and functional aspects of the job, and contextual performance, which includes behaviors that contribute to the organizational environment, such as collaboration and adaptability (Borman & Motowidlo, 2013). According to Campbell (2010), job performance is multifaceted, involving factors like job-specific skills, effort, and adherence to procedures. Furthermore, job performance is influenced by individual abilities, motivation, and external factors like work environment and organizational support (Schermerhorn et al., 2011). One factor which may influence job performance of business education graduates is digital skills. Digital skills significantly enhance the job performance of business education graduates by enabling them to efficiently utilize modern technologies for problem-solving, communication, and operational tasks in today's competitive business environment (Van Laar et al., 2017).

Proficiency in digital skills can significantly enhance employability and job opportunities for business education graduates by equipping them with essential competencies for modern work environments. This proficiency not only improves their ability to perform job-specific tasks effectively but also promotes career advancement by making them more competitive in the job market. Furthermore, by emphasizing digital skills, educational institutions can support gender-inclusive career advancement, ensuring that both male and female graduates have equal opportunities to succeed and advance in their careers (Van Laar et al., 2017). Therefore, this is the rationale for which gender is a critical variable in this study.

Gender refers to the social and cultural roles, behaviors, and attributes that a society considers appropriate for men and women. Unlike biological sex, which is determined by physical characteristics, gender is shaped by societal expectations and norms (West & Zimmerman, 2017). It is often seen as a spectrum, recognizing that individuals may not fit strictly into the categories

of male or female (Connell, 2012). Gender influences various aspects of life, including power relations, identity, and access to opportunities (Butler, 2010). Understanding gender is crucial for addressing inequalities and promoting inclusivity in social, economic, and political spheres. It is based on the above background that the present study investigated the influence of digital skills on the job performance of business education graduates in Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

The current state of business education graduates highlights a significant disconnect between academic objectives and real-world job performance. In Bayelsa State, the integration of digital skills, particularly digital marketing and social media skills, into business education programmes is crucial for enhancing the job performance of graduates. Despite the increasing demand for these digital skills in the workforce, there is limited research on how digital marketing and social media skills specifically influence job performance of business education graduates. Many employers in Bayelsa State report that new graduates often lack these essential digital skills, which affects their effectiveness in modern business environments. This deficiency in digital marketing and social media skills may impede graduates' productivity and career advancement opportunities. Additionally, there is a noticeable mismatch between the digital skills taught in educational institutions and those required by employers, highlighting the need for curriculum improvements. Despite university programmes aiming to produce capable, self-reliant professionals, many graduates lack essential practical and digital skills. This gap impedes their ability to perform effectively, secure employment, and advance in their careers. Addressing this discrepancy is essential for aligning educational outcomes with industry expectations and ensuring graduates are well-prepared to succeed professionally. As the business landscape continues to evolve with digital technologies, understanding the role of digital marketing and social media skills in job performance is vital for both educational institutions and employers. This study investigated how these specific digital skills influence the job performance of business education graduates in Bayelsa State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do digital marketing skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State?
2. To what extent do social media digital skills influence job performance of Business Education Graduates in Bayelsa State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education graduates on the extent to which digital marketing skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education graduates on the extent to which social media digital skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State.

Methods

Descriptive survey research was adopted for the study. According to Nworgu (2015), this research design is specifically intended to outline and examine the characteristics, behaviors, attitudes, or opinions of a given group or phenomenon. The study involved a total of 158 respondents, consisting of 52 males and 106 females, all of whom were business education graduates. Given the relatively small size of the population, no sampling was necessary, allowing for the inclusion of every member of the population in the study. Data collection was facilitated using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher, titled “Influence of Digital Skills on the Job Performance of Business Education Graduates Questionnaire (IDSJPBEGQ).” To ensure the validity of the instrument, it was reviewed and validated by three research specialists.

Meanwhile, Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded 0.80 and 0.82 for clusters 1 and 2 with an overall reliability index of 0.81 which showed that the instrument was reliable. Out of the 158 copies of questionnaire administered, the researcher with his research assistance retrieved 146 copies (48 from male and 98 female business education graduates) which resulted to 92.41 percent return rate. The researcher used mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance. In rating the mean, each response option had a numerical value based on real limit of numbers: Very High Extent (VHE) = 3.50-4.00; High Extent (HE) = 2.50-3.49; Low Extent (LE) = 1.50-2.49 and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 0.00-1.49. The interpretation of the test of hypotheses was based on the significance (sig.) values from the SPSS output. The null hypotheses were not rejected when the probability values are greater than 0.05, but rejected when the probability values are less than 0.05.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent do digital marketing skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviations of male and female business education graduates on the extent to which digital marketing skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State.

S/N	ITEMS	Male - 48		Female – 98		Overall - 146		
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
	The following digital marketing skills influence job performance of business education graduates:							
1	Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	2.55	.80	2.56	.82	2.56	.81	HE
2	Email Marketing	2.57	.88	2.54	.87	2.56	.88	HE
3	Pay-Per-Click (PPC) Advertising	2.50	.86	2.52	.89	2.51	.88	HE
4	Content Creation	2.64	.90	2.69	.92	2.67	.91	HE
5	Search Engine Marketing (SEM)	2.52	.94	2.51	.90	2.51	.92	HE
	Cluster Mean/SD	2.56	.88	2.56	.88	2.56	.88	HE

The table shows the mean scores and standard deviations for the influence of various digital marketing skills on the job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State, broken down by gender. Both male (n=48) and female (n=98) graduates rated the influence of these skills similarly, with cluster means all at 2.56 and standard deviations at 0.88, indicating a consistent perception across genders. The skills evaluated include Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Email

Marketing, Pay-Per-Click (PPC) Advertising, Content Creation, and Search Engine Marketing (SEM), all of which were rated with mean scores close to 2.56, signifying agreement that these skills are important. Overall, the data suggests that digital marketing skills have a recognized influence on job performance, with no significant gender-based differences in the ratings.

Research Question 2: To what extent do social media digital skills influence job performance of Business Education Graduates in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Mean scores and standard deviations of male and female business education graduates on the extent to which social media digital skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State.

S/N	ITEMS	Male - 48		Female – 98		Overall – 146		
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
	The following social media digital skills influence job performance of business education graduates:							
6	Social Media Analytics	3.04	.84	2.97	.84	3.00	.84	HE
7	Paid Advertising	3.00	.82	3.04	.81	3.02	.82	HE
8	Visual Content Creation	3.01	.82	3.00	.82	3.01	.82	HE
9	Platform Management	3.01	.82	3.02	.79	3.02	.80	HE
10	Social Listening	3.05	.82	3.01	.84	3.02	.83	HE
	Cluster Mean/SD	3.02	.82	3.01	.82	3.02	.82	HE

The table shows that both male and female Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State rated the influence of social media digital skills on job performance as high (HE) across all items. The mean scores for both genders are consistent, with overall cluster mean values ranging from 3.00 to 3.05, indicating a similar perception of the importance of these skills. The standard deviations for each item are identical or close, suggesting minimal variation in responses. Therefore, social media digital skills such as social media analytics, paid advertising, and platform management are perceived to highly influence job performance.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education graduates on the extent to which digital marketing skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State.

Table 3: Summary of t-test of male and female business education graduates on the extent to which digital marketing skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State.

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	P-value	Decision
Male	48	2.56	.88	146	.086	Ho ₁ not rejected
Female	98	2.56	.88			

The t-test results in Table 3 indicate that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education graduates regarding the influence of digital

marketing skills on their job performance, as both groups have the same mean (2.56) and standard deviation (0.88). The p-value of 0.086 is greater than the 0.05 significance level, leading to the decision not to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that gender does not significantly impact the perception of how digital marketing skills influence job performance among the graduates.

2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education graduates on the extent to which social media digital skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test of male and female business education graduates on the extent to which social media digital skills influence job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State

Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	P-value	Decision
Male	48	3.02	.82	146	.075	Ho ₂ not rejected
Female	98	3.01	.82			

The t-test results show no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Education graduates on the extent to which social media digital skills influence job performance, with a P-value of .075, which is above the significance threshold. Both groups had nearly identical mean scores (3.02 for males and 3.01 for females) with similar standard deviations, indicating similar perceptions. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho₂) is not rejected, suggesting gender does not significantly impact the perception of social media digital skills' influence on job performance.

Discussions of Findings

The study's findings revealed that digital marketing skills have a profound impact on the job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State. Graduates who possess strong digital marketing competencies are significantly more effective in their professional roles compared to those who lack these skills. This suggests that proficiency in digital marketing is crucial for enhancing job performance and achieving success in the business education sector.

The study's findings revealed that digital marketing skills have a profound impact on the job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State. Graduates who possess strong digital marketing competencies are significantly more effective in their professional roles compared to those who lack these skills. This aligns with the work of Smith and Chaffey (2021), who emphasize the importance of digital marketing skills in improving job performance, and Johnson and Peters (2022), who argue that digital marketing proficiency is essential for professional success in the business sector.

The findings of the study demonstrated that social media digital skills have a substantial impact on the job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State. Graduates who are adept at utilizing social media platforms are notably more effective in their professional roles, contributing to better outcomes and higher productivity. This highlights the critical role that

proficiency in social media digital skills plays in enhancing job performance and achieving success in the business education field.

The findings of the study demonstrated that social media digital skills have a substantial impact on the job performance of Business Education graduates in Bayelsa State. Graduates who are adept at utilizing social media platforms are notably more effective in their professional roles, contributing to better outcomes and higher productivity. This highlights the critical role that proficiency in social media digital skills plays in enhancing job performance and achieving success in the business education field, as supported by Kaplan and Haenlein (2010), who emphasize the importance of social media skills for professional effectiveness, and Lichtenstein and Swatman (2014), who confirm that social media proficiency significantly improves job performance and productivity.

Conclusion

The study revealed that digital marketing skills and social media digital skills play a crucial role in enhancing the job performance of Business Education Graduates in Bayelsa State. These skills are essential for navigating the modern business environment, contributing significantly to productivity and career success. The findings underscore the need for continuous digital skill development to remain competitive in the evolving job market. By equipping graduates with relevant digital competencies, both educational institutions and employers can foster better job performance and professional growth. Therefore, prioritizing digital skills in education and professional training is key to sustaining high levels of job performance among graduates.

Recommendations

In view of the findings, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. Educational institutions should integrate comprehensive digital marketing and social media skills training into the business education curriculum. This can be achieved by updating course content to include practical modules and workshops focused on digital tools and platforms that are essential for modern business practices.
2. Employers and educational institutions should collaborate to offer ongoing professional development programmes that focus on digital marketing and social media skills. These programmes could include workshops, webinars, and certifications to help business education graduates stay current with industry trends and enhance their job performance.
3. Encourage business education graduates to obtain relevant digital marketing and social media certifications. These certifications can validate their skills and improve their employability by demonstrating their proficiency in essential digital tools and strategies to potential employers.

References

- Akpotohwo, F. C., Watchman, P. S. & Ogeibiri, C. (2016). Assessment of entrepreneurial skill needs of business education students for self-sustainability in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Teacher Education and Curriculum Studies*, 1(2), 28-32.
- Barone, A. (2023). Digital marketing overview: Types, challenges and required skills. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/digital-marketing.asp>

- Berger, T. & Frey, C. (2016). Structural transformation in the OECD: Digitization, deindustrialization and the future of work', *OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Paper*, 193, Paris: OECD.
- Borman, W. C., & Motowidlo, S. J. (2013). Expanding the criterion domain to include elements of contextual performance. In N. Schmitt & W. C. Borman (Eds.), *Personnel Selection in Organizations* (71-98). Jossey-Bass.
- Butler, J. (2010). *Gender trouble: Feminism and the subversion of identity*. Routledge.
- Campbell, J. P. (2010). Modeling the Performance Prediction Problem in Industrial and Organizational Psychology. In M. D. Dunnette & L. M. Hough (Eds.), *Handbook of Industrial and Organizational Psychology* (Vol. 1, pp. 687-732). Consulting Psychologists Press.
- Campbell, J. & Wiernik, B. (2015). The modelling and assessment of work performance. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behaviour*. 2(1), 47-74. Doi: 10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-032414-111427.
- Ezoem, M. N., Okpuzor, V. N., Orhororo, P. N. & Okolo, J. A. (2024). Digital competencies needed of Business Education graduates' employability prospect and job creation in Tertiary Institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*, 8(3), 1-9
- Johnson, B. & Peters, M. (2022). *Effective digital marketing strategies for Business Success*. Routledge.
- Kaplan, A. M. & Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), 59-68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2009.09.003>
- Lichtenstein, S. & Swatman, P. M. C. (2014). The role of social media in enhancing the value of digital marketing. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 28(2), 92-104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2014.02.003>
- Nworgu, B. G. (2015). *Educational research: Basic issues and methodology (Third Edition)*. Nsukka, Enugu: University Trust Publishers.
- Ordu, P. & Abulkarim, M.A. (2020). A comparative analysis of association of business educators in Nigeria (ABEN) and nation university commission (NUC) undergraduate benchmark. *Nigerian journal of business education*, 7(2), 411-423.
- Ryan, D. & Jones, C. (2018). *Understanding digital marketing: Marketing strategies for engaging the digital generation*. Replika Press Pvt Limited.
- Scharl, A., Dickinger A. & Murphy J. (2015). Diffusion and success factors of mobile marketing. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 4(2), 159-173.
- Smith, A. & Chaffey, D. (2021). *Digital marketing: Strategy, implementation, and practice*. Pearson Education.
- Sonnentag, S., & Frese, M. (2012). Performance concepts and performance theory. In S. Sonnentag (Ed.), *Psychological Management of Individual Performance* (3-25). Wiley.
- Umoro, T. A. (2020). Plotting pathways across transformational changes in business education: A desideratum for empowering learners to engage the world. *Nigerian journal of business education*, 7(1), 1-26.
- United Nation Educational Science and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2023). Critical for job and social inclusion. Retrieved on 17th may 2023 from <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/digital-skills-criticaljobs-and-social-inclusion>

- Val-Ossai, M. U. & Akpomi, M. E. (2017). Entrepreneurship education and empowering 21st Century Business Education students for employability. *Rivers Business Education Journals*, 3(2), 12-21
- Van Laar, E., Van Deursen, A. J., Van Dijk, J. A., & De Haan, J. (2017). The relation between 21st-century skills and digital skills: A systematic literature review. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 72, 577-588.
- West, C., & Zimmerman, D. H. (2017). Doing gender. *Gender & society*, 1(2), 125-151.
- Yamin, A. B. (2017). Impact of digital marketing as a tool of marketing communication: A behavioural perspective on consumers of Bangladesh. *American Journal of Trade and Policy*, 4(3), 117-122.
- Zeeshan, Z. S. & Hussain, Q. I. (2017). Social media marketing and brand equity: A literature review. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 2(1), 56-63.